

Estimation of the adsorption coefficient of stearic acid in soil

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INTRODUCTION

This report documents the QSAR estimation of the adsorption coefficient (Koc) of stearic acid in soil was obtained using the Estimation Programs Interface Suite™ (EPI Suite) for Microsoft® Windows by the United States Environmental Protection Agency (US EPA) (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2012) which includes the Soil Adsorption Coefficient Program for Microsoft Windows (KOCWIN) in version v 2.0. Both estimation methods, based on the experimental log octanol-water partition coefficient (log Kow) and on Molecular Connectivity Index (MCI), were used.

The following information on chemical identity and log Kow (experimental Data Base of EPI Suite) of stearic acid were entered into the software:

Name: stearic acid
IUPAC name: Octadecanoic acid
CAS Number: 57-11-1
SMILES : O=C(O)CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC
Molecular formula: C18 H36 O2
Molecular weight: 284.5
log Kow (experimental DB): 7.17

RESULTS

Estimated (QSAR) Koc for stearic acid was 51050 L/kg (based on log Kow) or 11700 L/kg (based on MCI), indicating that the substance is immobile according to McCall et al. (1981) classification. However, adsorption values should be treated with caution since stearic acid is a ionisable substance, hence its Koc may be sensitive to soil pH.

REFERENCES

United States Environmental Protection Agency (2012). Estimation Programs Interface Suite™; (EPI Suite) for Microsoft™; Windows Version 4.1. Washington DC, USA.

McCall P.J., Laskowski D.A., Swann R.L., and Dishburger H.J., (1981), "Measurement of sorption coefficients of organic chemicals and their use, in environmental fate analysis", in Test Protocols for Environmental Fate and Movement of Toxicants. Proceedings of AOAC Symposium, AOAC, Washington DC.

APPENDIX

Output of KOCWIN estimation

SMILES : O=C(O)CCCCCCCCCCCCCCCC

CHEM : Octadecanoic acid

MOL FOR: C18 H36 O2

Koc may be sensitive to pH!

----- KOCWIN v2.00 Results -----

Koc Estimate from MCI:

First Order Molecular Connectivity Index : 9.770
 Non-Corrected Log Koc (0.5213 MCI + 0.60) : 5.6929
 Fragment Correction(s):
 * Organic Acid (-CO-OH) : -1.6249
 Corrected Log Koc : 4.0681

Estimated Koc: 1.17e+004 L/kg <=====

Koc Estimate from Log Kow:

Log Kow (experimental DB) : 8.23
 Non-Corrected Log Koc (0.55313 logKow + 0.9251) : 5.4774
 Fragment Correction(s):
 * Organic Acid (-CO-OH) : -0.7694
 Corrected Log Koc : 4.7080

Estimated Koc: 5.105e+004 L/kg <=====

 * NOTE: *
 * The Koc of this structure may be sensitive to pH! The estimated *
 * Koc represents a best-fit to the majority of experimental values *
 * however, the Koc may vary significantly with pH. *
